

A Review on Digital Marketing and Its Role in the Business

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Abstract

The function of digital marketing in the company has grown so important that most business models in the twentieth century are structured around their digital marketing campaigns. This study aims to determine whether a business requires digital marketing to boost sales and how much impact digital marketing has on business sales projected through their digital marketing. It examines the effect of digital marketing on audience as compared to traditional marketing strategies.

Keywords: Digital Marketing, Influencing, Reachability, Cost effectiveness

Introduction

We live in the digital age. Since the web revolution in the 1990s. One Internet connection channel was available during this operation - a personal computer. We now have a broad range of digital gadgets for it that could not have been envisaged those years ago. It seemed unimaginable that such a drastic change in social life could not have an impact on marketing (Monaco, 1999).

During the early years of widespread Internet use, it might also be used to share commercial information. Now our life is incomplete without the internet as it has become an opportunity for every individual. As a result, digital marketing emerged as a new branch of marketing science capable of providing various businesses with increasingly fresh avenues and capacities for establishing two-way engagement with their customers (Key, 2017).

Digital marketing is young enough category, which is still on the stage of frequent transformations. The biggest problem faced during marketing is generating leads and difficulties in finding the right audience which disturbs the budget of business and organization, and they are left with what ads need to run. Another reason is that it is so hard to perfectly create what type of content people want (Rogers, 2017)

Digital marketing is the part of advertising or online marketing, it is done using various technologies including computer, mobile, and online advertising with the help of the internet to promote or sell the desired product to the targeted audience on various digital platforms which include social media, Search Engine Optimization SEO, email marketing etc. (Bala, & Verma, 2018).

According to Vertail (2010), aside from the basic elements of digital marketing, which is the use of solely digital means for connection with the consumer, other details show the difference between digital and conventional marketing. For starters, the prices of traditional marketing channels (analog television, radio, periodicals, leaflets, billboards, exhibitions, etc) and digital marketing (search systems, social media, websites, video games, mobile applications, e-mail, digital art, etc.) differ due to their natural organization. Second, despite the infinite realm in which digital marketing runs, conventional marketing has a far greater coverage range. Third, unlike conventional marketing, digital marketing has no time constraints due to the absence of physical channels. Fourth, digital marketing exists primarily in the digital domain supporting two-way contact

between the firm and its customer Traditional marketing, on the other hand, lacks this capability from the start. Fifth, digital marketing allows businesses the ability to update and change material after it has been published. It is conceivable because of the digital environment in which such marketing exists and functions. Sixth, conventional marketing alone (or the integration of its components in the digital realm) enables the client to have a physical presence of products or services. Seventh, despite the so many benefits it provides, digital marketing is not equally beneficial for businesses in all sectors of the economy (Vertaim, 2010).

The key benefits of digital marketing in today's environment are interaction and the absence of geographical constraints simple access to resources attraction of the target audience to process operational assessment of the marketing campaign and real-time management (Piñeiro-Otero & Martínez-Rolán, 2016).

Reachability

We are seeing an increase in the acceptance of the digital platform as a marketing tool as the Internet and communication technology progress. This spike in digital marketing tool adoption is partly due to the significant dynamism in the flexibility and reachability that the digital platform provides (Kuberappa & Kumar, 2016).

As a result, we quickly compare the benefits of digital marketing tactics to those of traditional marketing instruments. Now the ai makes reachability of digital marketing to each social media user by detecting surrounding of the people and then start popping up the desired product on their news feed or on their search engine to increase the sale of the product artificial intelligence makes the reachability of the business to their targeted audience way more convenient, However, we are still in the early stages of AI's practical implementation by businesses in general, and by their marketing operations in particular. One may argue that we are even further along in the research process of thinking, theorizing, and investigating the application and impact of artificial intelligence (Arun HS Kumar, 2010).

Importantly, as with other big innovative technologies, AI's use in marketing raises practical and ethical concerns. Another quick reachability is social media marketing is also an essential component of public relations since an organization can use social networking sites to create relationships with key audiences and provide a range of organizational information through social media (Esch, Stewart, 2021).

Cost Effectiveness

Any business owner or marketer's prime aim is to promote their brand's products and services and improve brand awareness in the competition. We have seen how traditional marketing is giving way to internet marketing over the past few years. Why? Because digital marketing is a form of internet marketing, which is fresh and varied and is being used by many marketers to cut costs and concurrently reach a large audience. The widespread use of the internet. As technology advances, corporate marketing is simultaneously transforming its consumer-reach approach, making advertising more digital than ever (Ullah, 2022).

Several kinds of digital marketing tactics:

Let us take a closer look at just how digital marketing will affect your company's bottom line in 2022

- Email marketing
- YouTube marketing
- Soe tool
- Social media marketing
- Content marketing

The reasons why online marketing is more cost-effective are all outlined above. All the traditional advertising techniques, such as magazine covers, TV, and advertisements, are now antiquated and hugely expensive (Monika, 2019).

Return on Income ROI

Return on Income or ROI refers to the measurement of the Profit or Loss amount in a business that is being generated through the marketing campaigns. In simple words it is the sum of return on the capital that is invested in a business Marketing ROI means the practice of attributing profitability and profit growth to

marketing efforts. Organizations can calculate the return on the investment to indicate the degree to which trying to market efforts, either overall or campaign by campaign, contribute to revenue growth. Marketing ROI is a term that is frequently used to rationalize marketing spend and budgetary control for future and current campaigns and initiatives (Farris et al., 2015).

Influencing

In every way, the internet has altered the game. The inclusion of online capability has changed every element of modern living. The days of investing a sizable sum of money in conventional marketing strategies are over for businesses and marketing. Influence is the power to persuade someone to act, change their mind, or behave differently. Both directly (via persuasion) and indirectly are possible. However, the acts and changes that follow are always what defines it. People utilize influence for several purposes, some “good,” some “evil,” and some in between. Marketers adore influence because it is so potent. Marketers seek to work with the so-called influencers in a society where traditional advertising has less of an impact (Denton, 2021).

Influencer marketing does not depend on audience size. Results are what count. Especially in periods overlook that. Setting objectives and determining how to achieve them are the first steps in marketing. Many marketers overlook the fact that to involve significant customers, you must understand how they are, what they want, and how you may gain their support. Beyond contemporary influences, you should keep in mind that your goal is to deliver excellent customer service. Influence and brand advocacy are the results of that. The same as what you are doing with communities, give them room to expand (Solis, & Li, 2013).

Relationship between REACHABILITY and Digital Marketing:

A further benefit of digital marketing is that it facilitates communication with potential clients. Advertising to the users searching for our product or service is difficult using conventional means. But with digital marketing, we may concentrate on the customers who are most interested in our goods or services. It is challenging to connect with individuals who are interested in our business through conventional means (Opreana, & Vinerean, 2015). We wind up spending money on leads who might not be interested in our services or services. For instance, if we place a billboard on a road, we are advertising to anyone who uses the road, regardless of whether they are interested in our goods or services (Godin, 1999).

We can connect with customers who are interested in our company via digital marketing. We can target the customers who are interested in our products or services using these marketing strategies. We can reach out to people who we know are interested in our goods or services directly by running a PPC campaign that targets them explicitly. Instead of folks driving by our billboard, we can reach those who are actively looking for our type of business. We can choose a target audience, or the demographic we believe will be most interested in our company. We may advertise our business to customers who fit our target audience using this information. We can spend less time and money by using targeting. We will only be able to connect with customers. It will enable us to improve campaign outcomes and our company's return on investment.

Relationship between Effectiveness and Digital Marketing

Online marketing also makes it simple for we to track the success of our initiatives, as we will see when we examine the many functions of digital marketing. We want to know if marketing or advertising effort is producing results before we launch it (Chaffey, & Smith, 2013).

This is challenging with traditional marketing strategies since we cannot tell if our efforts were successful in persuading our audience. To find out how people heard about us, we would need to conduct a time-consuming poll with everyone that enters our store or calls our business. We may track the effectiveness of our efforts using digital marketing in real-time. There are several KPIs we may monitor. Impressions, traffic, clicks, dwell time, and conversions are some fundamental metrics (Desai, 2019).

We may calculate our ROI using these measures, which provide us with useful information about how well our campaign is working. We may use useful marketing tools like MarketingCloudFX when we are work with an internet marketing company like WebFX (Hoffman, & Fodor, 2010).

Relationship between ROI and Digital Marketing

The purpose of digital marketing is to maximize our financial return on investment. Online marketing is quite affordable compared to traditional marketing and provides a strong return on investment (ROI). Internally managed digital marketing is more expensive in terms of time than money. We can run our content marketing or social media marketing campaigns, but it will take a lot of work to develop, implement, track, and manage a successful campaign (Tiago, & Veríssimo, 2014).

Even if we spend on sponsored advertisements, the expenses are entirely under our control. We establish a budget that is practical for our company for PPC and social media advertising campaigns. It is crucial to understand that we get what we pay for, so we should create a budget that is appropriate for our business and sector. For our company, these digital marketing strategies offer an excellent return on investment (ROI). We may get a lot of money back by switching our budget from traditional marketing to digital marketing (Funk, 2014).

Relationship between Influencing and Digital Marketing

Digital marketing has long been regarded as an important medium for influencing customers; however, it should be distinguished from interactive behaviour such as liking and sharing product and services. While most of the research focuses on the impact of influence in digital marketing on business. On the other hand, social media influencers are making this role easier because they have a large audience that they can target at the same time without running multiple campaigns (Smith,2018).

Figure 1. *Conceptual Framework*

This framework indicates the significance of digital marketing in any business in this era and the also highlighting the crucial area of digital marketing in the business and help the business to reach their customer in their capacity and increase sales of the overall business and customer and keep interaction with customers through social media channel which help brands to optimize their business according to customer needs and wants.

Research Methodology

To study the role of digital marketing in business researchers first knows about the method analysis. Method of analysis is an essential component of the study because it includes various procedures and ideas that must be considered before actually beginning its research. Research design, which is the primary organizational

component of research, is crucial for providing the study with the proper focus and direction; it functions as a work schedule or road map that directs the study on the appropriate path (Dwivedi, 2020).

Trainee D (2019) said that the act of marketing your content and brand using social networking sites to enhance your business's reputation, attract customers, and increase brand value. Even though they are far from the only ones, Twitter, Facebook, Pinterest, and LinkedIn are all social media networks that may be used as an aspect of your advertising efforts.

It's used to respond to the problem's questions directly and assists in trying to answer logical questions. The cost of digital marketing is one of its main advantages. Digital marketing enables companies to increase leads and cut costs. Smaller businesses find it challenging to compete with larger corporations when using standard marketing strategies.

Large companies have the money to set aside for radio and TV commercials, among other things. Small firms find it challenging to compete as a result with these bigger businesses. However, digital marketing equalizes the playing field for all companies. Being an A cost-effective method of reaching out to potential customers. Several online marketing and advertising methods are inexpensive (Gondane & Pawar, 2021).

Additionally, it aids in deciding whether to conduct a qualitative or quantitative study, as well as how many people should be included in the sample and whether the study should be explanatory or descriptive. Overall, the best way to conduct research is to choose the best method. I have conducted data gathering for my research, followed by data analysis.

As a research tool, a series of questionnaires were created and utilized to collect data. The research design complies with the study's demand which calls for being ready to collect information from participants at a specific time. By using this technique, a predetermined sample of the chosen population will respond to questionnaires provided by the designated enumerator.

Research Design

According to Bryman and Bell (2007), a study design is a broad strategy that outlines the methods to be used for data collection and analysis. A quantitative cross-sectional research approach was used in the study. In a survey method, data is collected without altering the environment, but in a cross-sectional study, the unit of analysis is only encountered once. The cross-sectional study methodology has the benefit of allowing researchers to compare distinct analytical units in real time.

Sample size

Sample size may be measured as the number of respondents chosen to respond to research Questions or the quantity of items that reflect the entire community, whereas sample procedures are the approach or methods used by the researcher to generate a representative group. Gary (2008) defines sample size as the number of individuals selected from whom data was taken. He also notices that sample size may be characterized in a variety of ways; the first is the specified sample size, which is the number of sample units chosen for either data collection or contact. There is also the final sample size, which is the number of finished units for which data is gathered. If there is a significant non-response, disqualification, or both, the ultimate size of the sample may be significantly less than the stated sample size.

Targeted Population

The population and statistical significance of the survey will be addressed here, with the understanding that the demographic of each sample influences the boldness of the findings that will be acquired from the investigation. According to Sekaran and Bougie (2010), population refers to complete groups of individuals, events, or items of concern that the researcher desires to explore. The entire group of people or unit of analysis that researchers are interested in investigating to draw conclusions from is referred to as the target population. The target demographic for the study was the marketing students, employees who are linked with the marketing department and SMEs operating in Pakistan, which has many SMEs. This research depends on original data gathered through a well-structured questionnaire.

Data Collection

Data Collection method only with distribution of the surveys to the participants, the data collecting procedure was carried out in person. To gather data for the research study, a series of questionnaires were sent. In the study by Sabir et al. (2014), the researcher used a quantitative approach to data collection that allows us to summarize the findings. Because this sort of survey is simple to complete and allows for the collection of an unlimited number of replies, we are employing a fully working online Google form to collect the data. With this approach, the researcher was able to take on more respondent replies, and an online review was used to enhance the transmission and collection of the responses. Numerous topics, including demographic profiles and the structural studies started to examine, will be covered through the questionnaires. Researchers have gathered data at several significant store network locations. Participants are required to provide the responses they believe are most suitable and pertinent to the issues posed in the surveys. Using a suitable sample strategy, we are also using the likert scale. Respondents can indicate their agreement or disagreement with a study topic using likert scale questions. Likert scale questions allow responders to make rapid decisions, which increases their dedication and passion. Likert scale questions also make it easier to quickly code material for analysis.

Demographics/ Respondent Profile

This section contains background information about the respondents who participated in the study. It is divided into four parts: responders by gender, age, marital status, and qualification. This basic information was collected to identify the characteristics of the respondents and to show the demographic distribution in this study. This information is gathered in around 3 days. We were sent 70 surveys and received just 59 complete replies. The distribution is carried out, as seen in the table below.

Table 1**Demographics/Respondent Profile**

		Frequency	Weighted%
Age	Less than 21	11	18%
	21-30	30	49.2%
	31-40	14	23%
	41-50	5	8.2%
	51 and above	1	1.6%
	Total	61	100
Gender	Male	36	61%
	Female	23	39%
	Total	59	100
Qualification	Up to intermediate	10	16.9%
	Graduation	33	55.9%
	Masters	10	16.9%
	M.S/M.Phil.	3	5.1%
	PHD	3	5.1%
	Total	59	100
Marital Status	Single	37	62.7%
	Married	22	37.3%
	Total	59	100%

According to this table, the first section is representing the Ages of the respondent, so (49.2%) respondents are belonging to the 21-30 aged groups, between 31-40 age section are (24.6%), below 21 age group have (19.3%) respondents, 5 respondents are between the age group of 41-50 and at last we have elder age respondents that are 51 and above those respondents are (1.6%).

The second section is belonged to the Gender that represent how many respondents are Male and Female, so we come to know that our 39% respondents are Female, and 61% respondents are Male that shows females also entering the digital marketing sector.

Third section represents the qualification of our respondents, so our 55.9% respondents are Graduate, 16.9% are up to intermediate then 16.9% are also in the group of master's and only 3 people of all our respondents are doing M.S/M.Phil.

The last section represents the marital status of our respondents 37.3% people is married and 62.7% respondents are Unmarried. This section also represents that our most of the respondent are student.

Figure 2

As the pie chart above as figure 2, shown that 42.9% respondent often use social media for digital marketing, then 35.7% respondent use content marketing for increasing their business and 17.9% respondents are using digital ads for advertise their business, services, and products. Lastly only 2 respondents are using email marketing because there is a very low delivery rate, low open rate, and low click rate.

It necessary to measure the Return of Income (ROI) on all social media campaigns.

57 responses

Figure 3

In this above graph as figure 3, we are talking about the Return of Income (RIO), therefore, 56.1% respondent are agreeing with that ROI measuring is important on all social media campaigns and 7% respondent also strongly agree with this sentence. On the other hand, 19.3% respondents are selection 3 that is (neutral) so they aren't saying ROI is most important for social media campaigns. 8.8% are disagreeing with quote. Because some company either doesn't feel it's important to collect and analyze the data, or it simply doesn't think it has the resources to do so. Under most circumstances, the former case is much more likely than the latter.

Figure 4

This graph as figure 4, shows the data about how many people are agree that the digital marketing provide the better customer experience. Our 50.9% respondents are also agreeing 14% respondents strongly agree with this, then 19.3% are selecting neutral because they don't think that digital marketing give the best customer experience and 8.8% are disagree, 7% are strongly disagree because they think Too frequently, advertisements target those who would buy the product anyhow.

Digital marketing provides Customer satisfaction towards online shopping.

57 responses

Figure 5

In this above graph as figure 5, we can see how marketing gives the customer satisfaction with online purchasing. So, 49.1% respondent are choosing neutral because I think the most prevalent issue that buyers confront while purchasing online is that there is no assurance of a product's quality. 19.3% respondents are agreeing with this, 10.5% respondents are also strongly agreeing with digital marketing. 14% respondents are disagreeing and last but not the least 7% respondents are also strongly disagreeing because of the product quality, some logistic issues etc...

Figure 6

This graph in figure 6, represents that blogs or vlogs are important for social media marketing. 36.8% are choose 3 (neural), 33.3% respondant are selecting agree, 10.5% respondents are also choose the same thing, but on the other hand 12.3% are disagree and 7% also strongly disagree with this because they have some other ideas.

Figure 7

This above pie chart in figure, has shown that e-mail marketing still effective in business because it is now more relevant than ever. Despite the rise in popularity of social media and other messaging platforms, research suggests that email remains the greatest medium for reaching out to individuals. Email users are expected to increase more. So, our 56.4% respondents are agreeing with this, 18.2% respondents are not agreeing with this, and 25.5% respondents have not much idea about the email marketing effectiveness.

Social media increase the organic traffic to their online store.

56 responses

Figure 8

From total responses in figure 8, 48.2% respondents are agreeing that the social media increase that organic traffic to their online stores, 16.1% are strongly agree, 17.9% respondents are selecting neutral, 5.4% not agree with that and 12.5% also strongly disagree with that quote.

Digital marketing reach-ability to their targeted audience is easy approach.

56 responses

Figure 9

From total responses in figure 9, 89.3% respondents are agreeing with this because the chances of reach out to more customers in your target market by using digital marketing. You may target consumers who may have missed your original ad or want a bit more interaction before making a purchase by using specialized blog material, relevant social media channels, and search engine marketing. 10.7% respondents are do not agree with this quote.

Figure 10

In figure 10,our 80.4% respondents have believed that the future era is going to be digital, 8.9% respondent are choosing NO and last but not the least 10.7% respondents have no idea about the future digital.

Figure 11

In figure 11,our 42.9% respondents are agreeing that digital marketing enhance the sales, 12.5% are strongly agree with this, 23.2% are gave the answer with neutral selection, 8.9% respondents are disagreeing with this strategy and 12.5% are strongly disagree with this technique.

Figure 12

This graph in figure 12, shows that 14.3% respondents are said that digital marketing business can help increasing the profit in their business, 14.3% respondent selected digital marketing help in branding the business, 16.1% respondents are choosing digital marketing help to sustain in the market, last but not the least 48.2% respondent said all the option can help those businesses

Figure 13

In figure 13, from total responses, 47.4% respondents agreed that the ads are uploaded through social media can more effective than television ads. 12.3% are strongly agreed with this, 26.3% gave neutral respond, 5.3% disagree and 8.8% were strongly disagreeing. For each of the following areas listed, please tell us how effective you think these digital marketing activities.

Table 2

	Not Effective	Somewhat Effective	Effective	Very Effective
SEO (website or social media)	32	11	12	7
Google Ads	10	26	18	6
Facebook Ads	6	20	15	15
E-mail Marketing	7	23	16	12
LinkedIn Marketing	8	25	9	16
Others	8	21	13	12

In this table we examine how effective do you think these digital marketing activities. The first part of SEO, 32 respondents said not effective, 11 respondents said somewhat effective, and 12 respondents said SEO is effective, and 7 respondents said this most popular part. The second part is Google Ads 10 respondent said Google ads are no effective, 26 respondents said effective, 18 respondents said effective, and 6 respondents choose very effective.

Table 3

Impact of Digital Marketing on the Growth of SMEs

	Strongly Agree	Agree	Neutral	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
Email Marketing has greatly increased the revenue of business	21	23	11	2	3
Online advertising has increased the level of sales of any business	16	28	6	5	5
Search engine optimization has increased the level of sales in business	15	24	6	6	8
Mobile marketing has increased sales as well as market share of business	20	20	6	7	6

This table shows that the impact of digital marketing in small startups so, the first section is Email marketing (23) respondents agree that email marketing can increased the revenue. Second section is about the online advertising; our (28) respondents are agreeing that online advertising can increase the sale of our business. Third section is about SEO (search engine optimization) in this case our most of the respondents (24) agree with that SEO also increase the level of sales in every business. The last section of the table is about Mobile marketing as we can see most of the respondents are agreed with this section (around 40 respondents) because users must opt-in to receive communications, you may reach a highly focused audience and have direct marketing engagement with distinct client groups.

Table 4

Reachability of Digital Marketing

	Strongly Agree	Agree	Neutral	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
Would you say that digital marketing has a faster approach than traditional marketing?	24	27	5	3	1
Given choice of online marketing platforms, would you say digital marketing is more convenient than other traditional marketing media?	12	37	6	3	1
Would you say you have control of what is being advertised to you when it comes to digital marketing?	15	34	5	3	2
Would you say you have control of what is being advertised to you?	12	33	6	4	2
Does digital marketing provide greater prestige than print media?	15	32	6	2	4
Would you say digital marketing has helped you save time?	16	32	4	4	3
Would you say digital marketing at a greater advantage than traditional marketing (print) when it comes to being convenient?	17	32	4	4	3

Conclusion

The major motive behind this research is to identify the potential of role digital marketing in today's era and recognize the overall strength of digitalization in marketing to reach more in short span of time and reach more of their customer in different strategies which can be use in digital marketing which completely vanish the old school marketing style which we normally see on tv sequels. now the overall dynamics of marketing is shifting to electronic media like social media and people want to see everything on social media like Facebook and YouTube space which help people to target their customer in very economical way without spending million on tv ads which has limited reach to their customer but on the other hand every second person is on social media or a device which links with social media to target general audience or customer. for targeting a specific audience business use email marketing to keep them know about their business and continues sending a promotional deal on their email to keep them engage with their business. on the other hand, our general surveys indicates that the social media played a vital role that people have a platform different platform to reach different customer to get familiar with the product or services. Peoples survey also indicates that the reachability of marketing through digital marketing far more reachable than other medium of marketing. Most of the people answered the survey is belong to young generation or mostly are between twenty to thirty which prefer an online shopping which is most easy and without any hustle they shop without doing any sort of hustle in this busy environment. As a result, while digital marketing is difficult to sustain, with the advent of social media platforms such as Facebook and Twitter, organizations may still obtain the greatest results. It is not required to fight to put up a website to have an online presence; nonetheless, the tools indicated above might be useful in accomplishing this goal. The decisive point to mention is that strong and dependable legal regulations are needed to make digital marketing useful to organizations that rely on it. Its most thrilling of all business sports It is the fighting heart of any successful business. It is repeatedly changing in response to the explosion of information, the digital revolution, and the ferocity of competition at all levels and in all places. Digital marketing is incredibly important for businesses. In fact, as companies strive to reach customers online and increase sales, digital marketing has become an important focus for many. (Klosky, 2012)

Digital marketing is a type of marketing that employs a set of tools and methodologies to encourage industries or company's products and services. Digital marketing covers a broad range of marketing elements received via various channels and mediums (Martin & Todorov, 2010). Digital marketing is absolutely the way to go for any organization seeking to stimulate interest in its products on a world basis. As a contrary, digital marketing may not be simple to maintain, but due to advancement of social media tools like Facebook and Twitter, enterprises can still accomplish (Parkin ,2009). To establish a digital following, it is not necessary to fight to put it in there, and though the tools can be useful in achieving this goal. The ultimate point would be the importance of getting legal safeguards that will protect industry relies on digital marketing (Ryan & Jones, 2012)

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